

THE STATUS OF HUMAN DEVELOPMENT GENRE IN THE WORLD LITERATURE

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Annotation: This article is aimed to provide information about the role of the human development genre in world literature, its current state, the maturity of humanity and its role in the formation of a highly spiritual person in all respects. In addition, a number of books have been recommended that increase the motivation of the individual and promote new ideas.

Key words: genre, self-respect, culture, attitude, behavior, character, discipline, human development, personal growth.

Human development is a word that is used in the field of international development to describe the process of helping others. It entails investigations into the human condition, with the capacity approach serving as its central tenet. When the United Nations measures actual progress in human development, it uses the inequality adjusted Human Development Index as a metric. It is an alternate strategy to a single concentration on economic growth that is more concerned with social fairness as a way of interpreting progress than with economic growth alone. Human development can be defined as an increase in human capabilities, a diversification of options, an increase in freedom, and the fulfillment of human rights. This also refers to the process of mental and social development that occurs as a result of growing and experiencing things in life and learning new things.

Human development, according to the United Nations Development Program, is "the process of expanding people's choices," with those choices including "living a long and healthy life, being educated, and enjoying a decent standard of living," as

well as "political freedom, other guaranteed human rights, and various components of self-respect."

Self-improvement is a significant genre in American popular fiction, and this phenomena is inextricably linked to the United States' history, society, and philosophy. Self-improvement, according to the online Oxford Dictionaries, is "the process of improving one's knowledge, status, or character via one's own efforts." Self-improvement books are those that contain conversations about personal development. Wilson and Cash (2000, p. 120) report that millions of Americans seek "help, insights, and inspiration in resolving personal and interpersonal problems" from psychological self-improvement books. According to Dolby (2005), many Americans read self-improvement books in order to gain wisdom and live a fulfilling life.

This genre is becoming more prominent in Western Europe and Australia and some American self-improvement authors are also popular in China.

This genre is gaining popularity in Western Europe and Australia, and several self-improvement authors from the United States are also popular in China. According to Stine (1997, p. 7), human beings are perpetually on the lookout for ways to solve personal problems or improve their mental, physical, social, and professional skills, resulting in a constant demand for self-improvement and Bergsma describes this industry as a goldmine, or a lucrative one.

Attitude, Behavior, Character, and Discipline are the A, B, C, D's of life. A, B, C, and D are not only the fundamental letters of the alphabet; they are also fundamental characteristics of a human being. A good attitude toward anything is the way we think and feel about it. Our attitude conveys both positive and negative feelings about particular objects. A positive attitude about work is critical for success in life. Developing a positive attitude requires a sincere, honest, and self-affirming interpretation of life's circumstances. We can cultivate zeal, optimism, adaptability, self-esteem, confidence, self-control, and self-control. Our attitude reveals a great deal about who we are professionally and emotionally.

Our behavior is how we act in general, but particularly in relation to the situation or people we are with. Our behavior is influenced by a variety of factors, including culture, attitude, emotions, values, ethics, authority, and genetics. Our behavior should be easygoing and forgiving. Our personal behaviors significantly influence our career, business, goals, health, and relationships. It aids in the development of self-esteem, self-confidence, and a professional personality that benefits our personal growth. Thus, it is critical to cultivate and maintain a positive professional personality and demeanor.

The third one is character, which is the most important one in our lives because it determines our destiny. Character can be defined as the totality of an individual's qualities and attributes that distinguish him or her from others in a given situation. A person's character is actually an amalgamation of his or her characteristics that distinguishes him or her from others and helps him or her stand out from the crowd. It is also about cultivating one's inner self and striving to be a decent human being. When it comes to character, it is something that emerges from within and is frequently long-lasting. A positive character contributes to the development of a winning personality. To put it another way, a good character is the foundation of a captivating personality that attracts others. According to an old proverb, money wasted, opportunities missed, arrows shot, and character lost are all things that can never be recouped or replaced. Each individual's responsibility is to develop his or her character with the assistance of parents, instructors, or advisers. Teachers are critical. They contribute to character development and serve as role models for achieving personal goals they have already accomplished. A person with a good character will inevitably have a good personality.

Discipline is required in all aspects of life. Discipline is essential for success in any endeavor, whether it be employment or learning. Physical discipline, mental discipline, social discipline, and economic discipline are the four most significant sorts of disciplines to understand. We must engage in physical activity to be healthy and fit in order to develop Physical Discipline. The goal of mental discipline is to

keep the mind in a state of equilibrium. No one feels the need to be harsh or regressive in their behavior. Occupation, depression, and suppression were not intended by God when he created us. We must keep a sense of calm amid the situation. An individual's ability to maintain a balanced state of mind is extremely important.

Not all personal development books are made equal. Some help in starting you out on your journey, others give you a boost when you've achieved experience in certain areas. The following are the top personal development books that are suggested for everyone, regardless of their age:

For the beginning with “The Seven Habits of Highly Effective People” by Steven Covey is one of the most well-known bestseller. Covey's seven habits are composed of the primary principles of character upon which happiness and success are based. The book “The Seven Habits of Highly Effective People“ puts forward a principle-centered approach to both personal and interpersonal effectiveness. Rather than focusing on altering the outward manifestations of your behavior and attitudes, it aims to adapt your inner core, character, and motives.

The seven habits he mentioned in the book are as follows:

1. Be proactive
2. Begin with the end in mind
3. Put first things first
4. Think win/win
5. Seek to understand first, before making yourself understood
6. Learn to synergize
7. Sharpen the saw

Other notable works in the personal development genre include "Eat That Frog" which is one of the best books about productivity and overcoming procrastination written by Brian Tracy. It is packed with concrete suggestions and covers the twenty-one most potent personal efficiency principles. These tactics, methods, and strategies are all realistic, time-tested, and effective. Numerous similar concepts can be applied

to your personal life as well. The frog analogy comes from Mark Twain, who stated that if you can start your morning by eating a live frog, you'd have tackled the worst thing that can happen that day. The frog is the most critical task—the one people are most inclined to put off, but which has the greatest impact on their outcomes.

“Think And Grow Rich” by Napoleon Hill is another helpful work for those who want to become improved personally. One of the best aspects of this book that distinguishes it as an "ultimate guide to success" is that it discusses the type of desire required to reach your goal. Additionally, it discusses the need of being absolutely clear about the sacrifices necessary to obtain our desired outcome. As a result, it is one of the first books that are frequently recommended by a large number of people attempting to grow or become rich.

To conclude, Personal development has always been important. It is of great importance in the development of people as a harmoniously developed person, in finding their place in life, in achieving great success and in maintaining constant motivation. The desire of reading the bestseller books of writers, motivators and businessmen, who have made a significant contribution to the genre of human development, is growing year by year. Above mentioned books are of this sort and we can make more of this list.

LIST OF USED LITERATURES:

1. Bergsma “Do self-help books help?” 2008, p 342
2. Bassett, J. (2008). The Future of Humanities Education, or Ahab and His Humanities. *Interdisciplinary Humanities*, 25(1), 7–19.
3. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/307967692_PERSONAL_DEVELOPMENT